

Leveraging Client-side Computation for Biomedical Machine Learning Inference with Open Neural Network Exchange

Abstract

Biomedical settings often involve large datasets and sensitive information confined within institutional boundaries that limit outbound data transfers. Low-resource areas with limited biomedical resources and unreliable internet access also struggle to forward their data for computation. This paper advocates for executing machine learning models locally on conventional computers leveraging new technologies such as Open Neural Network Exchange. The proposed design enables secure, client-side execution without data transfer, addressing privacy and bandwidth constraints while enhancing the portability of biomedical models execution.

1 Introduction

Biomedical settings showcase a growing number of data-driven platforms for processing biomedical records in the form of tabular and imagery data, among others [2]. Moreover, these tasks frequently entail sizeable datasets and sensitive information that hinders their transfer outside the institutional boundaries where data is stored.

Artificial intelligence (AI) solutions are particularly promising for low-resource or rural settings with a shortage of medical specialists. However, these settings often also lack access to a reliable, safe, and stable internet connection [7].

The current mainstream paradigm for computation entails transferring data to a server for its computation, offloading resource allocation and software setup tasks from the client. However, moving large amounts of data not only requires abundant bandwidth for its transfer but also poses privacy

and regulatory challenges regarding the location of the transferred data, especially with sensitive healthcare datasets [8]. Thus, the application of the most recent technologies in AI to healthcare and biomedical institutions collides with the above constraints characteristic of biomedical settings.

This work proposes benefiting from existing technologies to avoid aforementioned hurdles, easing data privacy concerns by bringing machine learning (ML) model inference to the client. This new design involves no data transfer of sensitive information and instead requires the model to be executed locally in conventional computers.

To achieve this goal, we propose employing ML models converted to Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX) format for its client-side execution through web technologies, i.e. employing a website [1]. ONNX enables model portability for increased interoperability of AI tools. This format is widely supported by many popular frameworks such as MATLAB, CoreML, PyTorch, and Keras, among others. The project ONNX Runtime is a cross-platform ML model accelerator allowing running ONNX models in different hardware, such as iOS or Android devices, thanks to a flexible interface for running models in both CPU and GPU by leveraging WebAssembly, WebGL and WebGPU technologies. Therefore, ONNX Runtime enables client-side execution of ML models thanks to a JavaScript interface [3].

2 Case Study

The automation of biological image analysis plays a pivotal role in accelerating biomedical research. The research of intricate conditions like neurodegenerative diseases requires substantial volumes of data. High-throughput high-content screening (HTHCS) offers a platform for such large data acquisition [5]. Furthermore, the digitisation of tradi-

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Figure 1: Interaction diagram between server and client. The conventional approach sends the files for its use in the server which responds with the predicted class. Conversely, the proposed solution only requires downloading the ML model to the client for its local execution.

tional measurements in hospital environments, including clinical records, radiology, histopathology, and physiology measurements, has produced a deluge of digital data. The advent of new sensors not only facilitates the acquisition of novel data but also augments this influx [4].

High-throughput screening (HTS), predominantly used in disciplines like drug discovery, has been instrumental in this exponential growth of data in biomedical contexts. Deep learning (DL) offers significant advantages in managing and enhancing the quality control (QC) of a vast array of images derived from HTHCS scenarios. Common challenges with these images, such as out-of-focus segments and inconsistent density fluctuations within assay plates, can be deftly handled using DL. Moreover, prediction models, driven by this extensive data and sophisticated algorithms, hold the potential to revolutionise healthcare. They offer promise in better disease prevention, more accurate diagnoses, and personalised treatment recommendations, paving the way for a more proactive and precise approach to patient care.

Armed with these QC metrics, researchers can efficiently pinpoint and rectify image discrepancies, ensuring data purity and thereby, the reliability of their experimental outcomes.

The proof of concept presented in this work portrays an automated QC system¹. The QC model was trained on fluorescent microscopy images of the rosella biosensor, captured within an HTHCS framework [6]. This model aimed to discern density variations, categorising them as good, semi-

covered, or bad (see Figure 2). This convolutional neural network (CNN) model was stored in ONNX format using PyTorch.

Figure 2: Examples of the three density classes: Covered (a), semi-covered (b) and bad density (c). These examples have been extracted from the public repository Image Data Resource (IDR) [9].

3 Conclusion

The proposed design enables seamless use of ML models between biomedical institutions, alleviating data privacy concerns. The proposed design requires fewer server-side resources, eliminating computational bottlenecks, and avoiding regulatory constraints. This design is particularly advantageous for academia and low-resource settings, easing ML clinical validation in various settings, especially those with limited resources. Moreover, the employment of web technologies eliminates the need to update client-side standalone applications and leverages a highly portable application widely available (the web browser).

¹<https://carlosvega.github.io/CellAnalyzerPoC/>

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